

TASHKENT MOSAIC AS AN ASSET FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

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INTRODUCTION

Mosaic of Tashkent is an integral part of the unique image of the city and reflects values of different cultures. This study is aimed at studying the Tashkent Mosaic and determining its value as a tourist asset. In the course of the study, survey was conducted to determine the interest of local and foreign travelers for this object, and history that caused the creation of mosaic was studied. Furthermore mosaic locations that are scattered throughout the city were also studied and a convenient map was developed.

This research also emphasized recommendations for attracting tourists to this asset and indicated the target audience of the created route.

HISTORY

The earthquake of 1966 and the ensuing fraternal help of all the Union republics, the cities of Moscow and Leningrad, the regions of Uzbekistan, military builders, in many ways contributed to the beginning of radical reconstruction and development, the formation of the architectural and artistic appearance of Uzbekistan.

In Tashkent, five house-building plants are starting to operate, producing a series of 7 and 9 storey residential buildings, and the base of large-panel houses is expanding. The creative team "Tashgiprogor" faces new challenges: in addition to brick 4 and 5 storey and panel houses, 9 and 16 storey buildings of various designs are being designed: frame buildings, by means of lifting ceilings, monolithic, mixed and others.

In the 1970–80s, housing construction was actively developing.

Glavtashkentstroy construction organizations are taking measures to strengthen their industrial base. In connection with the transition to industrial rails and stream construction, architectural and urban problems are becoming more complicated.

Housing estates Yunusabad, TTZ, Kuylyuk, Ts17-18, Chilanzar, Algoritm and many other objects were built according to the projects of the Tashgiprogor Institute. Architects G Korobovtsev, A. Kosinsky, A. Khurshudov, E. Malichenko, N. Abdurakhimov, E. Iskhakbaev, N. Pushkaryova, S. Shuvaeva and artists Zharsky made a great contribution to housing development during this period of time.

HISTORY

In Tashkent, the Zharsky brothers came to the 70s, to rebuild the city after a strong earthquake of 1966. They worked at the plant of reinforced concrete products by artists. In Uzbekistan, with the use of ancient stylistic traditions, they created significant works. Brothers worked in DSK No. 2 for more than 20 years. On their account are at least 400 decorated multi-storey residential buildings. The eldest of the brothers Peter, a monumentalist by education, began this work. He saw a large field of activity on the gray walls, that is, "in gray concrete canvases". His first panel for a 9-storey residential building on the street Mukimi caused a "light shock" among architects.

On the ends of five-story and nine-story fiberglass mosaic panels were created according to sketches, under the supervision of Zharsky. As a result, Tashkent, at the initial typical development, due to the variety of colors and oriental ornamentation, acquired a special originality. In 1970-1990, it was the creative collaboration of the Zharsky brothers with then-famous architects that yielded remarkable results and made it possible to talk about the "Tashkent style" of construction, a kind of, unlike the others. A characteristic feature of the Uzbek mosaic is oriental patterns. They form independent ornaments or frame finished plots devoted to great achievements, friendship of peoples, heroes of labor and individual professions.

In the USSR, this was a common phenomenon - a mosaic panel. This phenomenon was ubiquitous, but it stopped, now it is an unacceptable luxury for the developer - an artistic decoration of the building. Architects tried to give individuality to each building; they spared no money for this type of art.

In addition to monumental end mosaics, decorations were made on the eaves of facades, in the inter-window spaces, on the walls above the entrance and near it, at bus stops, metro stations, stairs, fountains, facades of kindergartens and departmental institutions.

Small panels were placed at the entrances of typical nine-story buildings. Often these were geometric or floral oriental patterns, abstract or animalistic plots. Wall panels served not only as decoration, but also as a propaganda tool. Often there were symbols of that era, stories on the topic of pioneering, universal equality and fraternity, friendship. Today, many of them are sealed with ads or covered with paint during repairs.

SURVEY

Methodology

Objectives

The present study is based on international researches that can be applied to the case (Shih, 2006; Taylor, Kim & Chan, 2018; Wang & Nakano, 2019) having as principal objective the analysis of interest towards Soviet art in general and mosaic in particular. Among specific objectives we can name:

- Analysis of factors that can attract tourists in mosaic art itinerary in Tashkent;
- Determination of people's interest in history, art and culture of Tashkent;
- Identification of correlation (if there is any) between demographical, psychological and other characteristics of participants in the study and their interest in mosaic art in Tashkent;
- Suggestion of ways of mosaic integration into traditional touristic offer in Tashkent.

Instruments

To analyze interest of local residents and international tourists in mosaic art in Tashkent and evaluate the necessity of itinerary creation that can include different representative locations with Soviet mosaic, an online-based survey was conducted. The survey was created in Microsoft Forms platform in three languages: Uzbek, Russian and English.

The questionnaire consists in several parts.

The first part includes questions that help to determine demographic characteristics of participants in the survey: gender, age, country of residence, occupation. The next part is measuring with Likert scale the general interest of the participants in history, culture, paintings, architecture, Soviet history, mosaic, graphics, modern art, Soviet art. The following questions are analyzing the factors that can attract people in touristic itinerary or excursion on Tashkent mosaic art. Among the factors are listed artistic value of mosaic itself, possibility to learn something new about interesting places in Tashkent or about Tashkent history, to spend time outdoors or to meet new people interested in the same topic.

The Likert scale was applied also in measurement of the factors that can influence on city tour choice: excursion duration, topic, entertainment, historical or cultural component, distance between different itinerary points or transportation between those. Also, the survey measured the time participants are ready to dedicate to the type of excursion offered, the transportation preferred and the frequency of going to Tashkent city tours. Finally, the participants evaluated their interest in visiting different cultural places and events, such as exhibitions, galleries, theaters, concerts, etc.

The questionnaire was validated twice. First, by people not involved in the research to ensure that the translation of questions is understandable and there is no ambiguity or misinterpretations. Second, on reduced group of 10 participants in each case, so the researchers checked the understanding of the questionnaire. Also the answers of test groups gave data for Cronbach alpha calculation (0.86), needed to prove the validity of the survey.

The questionnaire was distributed through connections networks of the researchers. Data collection was done in February 2020.

Data analysis was conducted with IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 23 (IBM Corp., 2018).

Participants

In total, 218 people participated in the survey. The majority (61.1%) are local residents, the others proceed from Russian Federation, European Union, Latin American countries and Kazakhstan.

57.8% of participants are females; age distribution shows that 76.6% out of 218 people are between 19 and 35 years old.

The distribution in terms of language shows that Russian speakers represent the major part of the pool: 70.2%.

Results

The results of the analysis show the following. First, the participants demonstrate moderate interest in artistic value of mosaic, ranking it in with 1.48 out of 3 (SD = 0.65). The topic of the excursion (2.68, SD = 0.2) and the mode of transportation between different points (2.49, SD = 0.13) are very important and can influence on choice of a particular itinerary. Almost half of the participants (48.2%) preferred to follow itinerary by foot, while 32.6% choose group bus excursions.

79.8% of all participants in the survey confirmed that they had never been on any Tashkent city tour or thematic excursion. The majority of them are Uzbekistan residents, while international participants stated having previously this type of experience.

The analysis shows positive correlation between interests of participants and their attraction towards mosaic art excursions. Those who are interested in art museums ($p=0.871$), modern music concerts ($p=0.794$) and exhibitions ($p=0.725$) demonstrated the biggest rate in that case. No correlation was found between interest in Soviet art or Soviet history and mosaic itinerary.

No dependency on gender was found, however there is weak negative correlation between interest of participant in topic and age ($p= -0.094$). Younger people show a bit more interest in mosaic art, while elder people do not give such a big importance to it.

Occupation and profession do not show any influence on level of interest of participants.

Limitations and ideas for future research

Reduced number of participants cannot let us extrapolate the results obtained to the whole population of Uzbekistan. However we can find several tendencies that can help in the process of mosaic itinerary creation.

The research was conducted on the basis of quantitative data, while it could be interesting to conduct in-depth interviews with participants and analyze deeper their interest in mosaic art in Tashkent. Therefore we can consider the results of research as an initial step provided general information about potential tourists' ideas and expectations, at the same time giving insight on characteristics that will be shared by target audience.

Conclusions

The results of the study demonstrate an interest in mosaic art among local and international residents. The analysis has determined specific characteristics of people interested in the topic that can be used to attract them as participants and create itineraries. Among them are attraction to culture, concerts and need for entertainment.

On the other hand, data show that due to dispersion of mosaic throughout the town and preferences of potential participants in the itinerary, it will be more recommendable to include the points of proposed itinerary in other touristic routes in the town, creating additional value for them. A thematic mosaic itinerary can be difficult to manage in terms of customer interest, as the results demonstrate that the target audience will presumably include only the specialists in the topic. The number of people with those characteristics is reduced, so to cover more customers we have to widen the offer and provide a mixture of experiences for tourists.

LOCATIONS

The map with the locations and pictures of Tashkent city's mosaic panels was developed. This map can be used as a guideline for touristic itinerary.

The creation of map was divided into 3 operations. The first was finding the exact location of mosaic panel, which was followed by indicating this point in pre-created page in Google Maps. The final step was taking photo of mosaic art in order to get a photo-preview of the location on the map. Since all locations are scattered, it can be easily to create a personal route taking into account time, destination and transportation.

This online map consists of 22 mosaic arts. Next stage of the project is to find other mosaic panels and place them in this online map.

